

CAPABLE

Cancer Patients Better Life Experience

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Versions History

Version	Date	Author	Comments
1.0	15 th November 2023	UPM	Table of Content
2.0	30 th January 2024	UPM	Preliminary version of the document
3.0	15 th February 2024	UPM, UNIPV	Updates on HTA
4.0	10 th March 2024	UPM, UNIPV	Cost analysis
5.0	25 TH March 2024	UPM	Final version

Executive Summary

The document reports the activities of Health Technology Assessment and the overall result of the standards and regulation specific to the field of Digital Health.

This report has been organized into 2 parts that are summarized below.

The first part provides a report on the health technology assessment, following a method proposed by the EU network of HTA (HTA CoreModel) and analyzing the proposed technology under different viewpoints that are:

- The current clinical context which details the clinical problem and the current available solutions and approaches.
- Description and technical characteristics of the solution shortly presents the CAPABLE solution.
- Safety aspects are described as incidental findings and risks associated with the use of CAPABLE.
- Clinical effectiveness of the solution, which briefly describes the main result of the clinical study.
- Cost and economics that depicts the overall costs for the deployment of the solution.
- Ethical analysis details the solutions that were adopted during the pilot studies to prevent or address any ethical issue.
- Organizational aspects section details the requirement at organizational level to uptake the solution.
- Patients and social aspects section details the burden of patients and caregiver and how a system like CAPABLE is perceived.
- Legal aspects details the legal frameworks to be followed in order to use the CAPABLE solution.

The second part of the document focuses on the standardization practice considering two levels:

- Standardization of the information managed by the CAPABLE system.
- The required standardization following the Medical Device Regulation.

HTA analysis report

The health technology assessment (HTA) plays a crucial role in evaluating the effectiveness, safety, and value of healthcare technologies, treatments, and interventions. Through a systematic and evidence-based approach, HTA provides decision-makers with the information needed to make informed choices about the adoption, reimbursement, and use of healthcare technologies within healthcare systems.

In this document the authors will use the model proposed by the EU network of HTA that defines a tool called HTA Core model¹.

Current clinical context

Cancer is the leading cause of death for people under 70 years in most of the countries worldwide, accounting for nearly 10 million deaths in 2020. Cancer is a complex disease that causes late and long-term side effects due to the malignancy of the condition and the treatment; this reduces the quality of life of the patient and families and generates a significant social and economic burden. In many cases the cancer patients receive a treatment (e.g., immunotherapy, chemotherapy) to be followed out of the hospital; and it is crucial to accurately follow-up the treatment response, the overall cancer evolution and the patient's side effect. If a patient is having a good evolution, he/she will have periodic visits every 3 months. The duration of the visit is around 20 minutes, which in some cases is not enough to address all the issues of a patient.

Melanoma and immunotherapy

The European incidence of malignant melanoma varies from 3–5/100000 in Mediterranean countries to 12–35/100000 in Nordic countries. The incidence of melanoma has been rising steadily over the last 40 years². In recent years, the introduction of immunotherapy with immune checkpoint-inhibitors (ICIs) have significantly improved the outcome of melanoma patients and have become standard of care³. However, immunotherapy treatment is associated with specific immune-related adverse events (irAEs). irAEs possibly result in a diminished health-related quality of life (HRQoL)⁴. With immunotherapy becoming standard care in advanced melanoma patients, an increasing number of patients experience symptoms of irAEs, most commonly occurring in skin, liver, gastrointestinal, pulmonary and endocrine organs. Inadequate symptom monitoring and reporting might lead to worsening of the adverse events and also more frequent emergency department visits and hospital admissions⁵.

Renal Cell Carcinoma treatments

Kidney cancer accounts for 5% and 3% of all adult malignancies in males and females, respectively, representing the seventh most common cancer in men, and the tenth in women⁶, corresponding to about 400000 patients globally each year, and 115000 patients in Europe. Renal Cell Carcinoma (RCC) accounts for about 80% of all kidney cancers.

¹ <https://www.eunetha.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/HTACoreModel3.0-1.pdf>

² Hollestein, L.M., van den Akker, S.A.W., Nijsten, T., et al. (2012) Trends of cutaneous melanoma in The Netherlands: increasing incidence rates among all Breslow thickness categories and rising mortality rates since 1989. *Ann Oncol*, 23(2), 524–530.

³ Haanen, J. B. A. G., Carbone, F., Robert, C., et al. (2017) Management of toxicities from immunotherapy: ESMO Clinical Practice Guidelines for diagnosis, treatment and followup. *Annals of Oncology*, 28 (Supplement 4), i119 – i142.

⁴ Rogiers, A., Boekhout, A., Schwarze, J. K., et al. (2019) Long-Term Survival, Quality of Life, and Psychosocial Outcomes in Advanced Melanoma Patients Treated with Immune Checkpoint Inhibitors. *Journal of Oncology*, 2019, 1 – 17.

⁵ Vandyk, A.D., Harrison, M.B., Macartney, G., Ross-White, A., Stacey D. (2012) Emergency department visits for symptoms experienced by oncology patients: a systematic review. *Support Care Cancer*, 20, 1589 – 1599.

⁶ Siegel RL, Miller KD, Jemal A. Cancer statistics, 2016. *CA Cancer J Clin* 2016;66:7-30

Tyrosine kinase inhibitors targeting vascular endothelial growth factor receptors (VEGFRs) have been the first-line standard of care for the last decade⁷; however, almost all patients acquire resistance over time. The recent introduction of immune checkpoint inhibitors has further improved the outcome of those patients. Presently, the monoclonal antibody Nivolumab, and its immune combination with the Ipilimumab have been registered for use in patients refractory to VEGFR-targeting agents as well as in the first line treatment of patients with poor or intermediate risk features. Furthermore, combinations of immune checkpoint inhibitors with anti-VEGFR agents⁸ are emerging as novel treatment options. Immune checkpoint inhibitors have a specific toxicity profile which is challenging the historical oncologists' practices. Indeed, the clinical management of these often ill-defined irAEs is new to many oncologists. Moreover, despite most of them remaining mild in intensity, around 10% of patients treated with these agents will develop severe, sometimes life-threatening, dysimmune toxicities⁹.

Electronic symptom monitoring during cancer treatment.

The referral of patients developing immunotherapy-related toxicities, together with their prompt and aggressive treatment is thus mandatory to maximize the likelihood of both resolving these adverse events, as well as safely continuing the anticancer treatment. The collaboration of patients, who must be informed of the need of referring any unusual sign or symptom to their oncologist, is thus crucial, as it is an instrument which could help the patients in this matter.

An approach to improve symptom control can be the collection of symptom information through patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs). Furthermore, symptom self-reporting and monitoring is associated with improved clinical outcomes¹⁰. Moreover, several web-based monitoring systems have also been shown to intensify symptom management, improve symptom control and improve overall survival¹¹.

Existing technology.

Most of the monitored solutions allow symptom reporting and remote patient monitoring and specific notifications are sent to care providers.

Untire app¹² provides support to patients to manage the fatigue side effect and offers a comprehensive lifestyle intervention to improve mental health, nutrition and physical activity habits. Kaiku health¹³ represent one of the most comprehensive solutions available in Europe and currently is making a partnership with Electa¹⁴ a MedTech that provides devices for radiotherapy, radio surgery and other solutions. Electa has a specific portfolio of services and products in the field of oncology and it integrates the Kaiku technology to add value to the therapy and to improve the follow up of patients. Another solution is the German Cankado pro-react-onco¹⁵ (class I MD) that provides a telehealth solution to monitor evolution of cancer and an app that provides daily support to patients, allowing symptom reporting, behavioral advices and AI driven decision support and Incident

⁷ Canino C, Perrone L, Bosco E, et al. Targeting angiogenesis in metastatic renal cell carcinoma. *Expert Rev Anticancer Ther* 2019;19:245-257

⁸ Rini BI, Plimack ER, Stus V, et al. Pembrolizumab plus Axitinib versus Sunitinib for Advanced Renal-Cell Carcinoma. *N Engl J Med* 2019;380:1116-1127

⁹ Champiat S, Lambotte O, Barreau E, et al. Management of immune checkpoint blockade dysimmune toxicities: a collaborative position paper. *Ann Oncol* 2016;27:559-574

¹⁰ Basch E., Deal, A.M., Kris, M.G. (2016) Symptom Monitoring With Patient-Reported Outcomes During Routine Cancer Treatment: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 34 (6),

¹¹ Denis, F. (2017) Randomized Trial Comparing a Web-Mediated Follow-up With Routine Surveillance in Lung Cancer. *Journal of The National Cancer Institute*, 109 (9).

¹² <https://tiredofcancerapp.com/>

¹³ <https://kaikuhealth.com/>

¹⁴ <https://www.elekta.com/>

¹⁵ <https://cankado.com/>

prediction to assess the evolution of the disease of the patients. This solution has different Pharma companies as partners (Roche, Pfizer, Novartis, MSD).

Another solution in the market to monitor side effects is to exploit general solutions for telemedicine and teleconsultation to support patients during oncology treatment. A very famous American brand is Huma¹⁶ that provides services of teleconsultation, remote follow up, gathering of vital signs. This solution is widely used in the USA and UK (in the UK it is part of the NHS digital toolkit). Another interesting solution is Ticuro¹⁷ (from Italy), a general telehealth solution used to monitor different conditions, offering a teleconference service, remote monitoring of physiological signals (using IoT technology) and supporting the execution of care plans defined by the specialists.

Proposed technology

The CAPABLE solution is a digital intervention to foster the outpatient management of cancer. It targets patients and oncologists. The patient system is composed of a smartphone app and a smartwatch (Asus VivoWatch) that are used to gather physiological and health information (Patient reported experience and outcomes - PREM, PROM) to monitor the health status of the patients during a specific cancer treatment. The app provides guidance on how to manage side effects and suggests behavioral modifications to promote the overall wellbeing of the patients, with the goal of improving their quality of life. The oncologists can remotely follow up the health status of the patients and use a clinical decision support system that implements the current clinical practice guidelines (Computer Interpretable Guidelines) for the management of therapy and side effects.

Description and technical characteristics of technology

CAPABLE is an eHealth tool to monitor symptoms of systemic treatment, coach patients during their cancer journey and offer information and interventions with the main endpoint to improve quality of life. CAPABLE is made up of several components that run in the back-end of the system. Figure 1 shows the overall structure of the CAPABLE system, whereas Figure 2 shows the components and their connections in the CAPABLE environment. Each component of the CAPABLE system was deployed on a Virtual Machine (VM) provided by the hospital and thus accessible inside the hospital's internal network under hospital security policies and rules. Each VM was managed by the project partner responsible for the development of the specific component. Access to the VMs was possible through dedicated Virtual Private Networks (VPNs) set up by hospital IT staff and regulated by Data Transfer Agreements (DTAs) in place between the clinical center and each project partner.

¹⁶ <https://www.huma.com/>

¹⁷ <https://www.reply.com/ticuro-reply/en/>

Figure 1: Overall structure of the CAPABLE system

Figure 2: The CAPABLE architecture with the components involved

The detailed description of the component’s functionalities, their interactions, are described in D4.3.

During the capable studies, the CAPABLE patient app was provided to patients either on a smartphone purchased by the project or on the patients’ own devices in case these are compatible with the app installation requirements (Android version 11). The smartphones of the project were given to patients with the app already installed, whereas for personal

smartphones a member of the CAPABLE research staff performed the installation during enrollment. In all cases, the research staff participated in the enrollment visit to support the patient in the first login and setup of the system.

Through the app, patients can report symptoms and adverse events related to treatment, access educational material and perform wellbeing interventions. To improve the mental and physical wellbeing of patients, CAPABLE implements non-pharmacological evidence-based interventions called Virtual Capsules. Such interventions focus on sleep/fatigue improvement, acceptance and expression of the cancer journey and positive thinking. Virtual Capsules are developed using behavioural models, to help patients turn the proposed interventions into healthy habits.

The project provided patients also with a ASUS VivoWatch SP HC-B05 smartwatch, setup during enrollment by the research staff. To ensure proper communication with the ASUS cloud platform (Omnicare), an additional application (OmniCare Hub, provided by ASUS) was installed on the smartphone.

The information entered in the app by the patients is also made available to healthcare professionals through the physician web application. The web application is accessible by users only in the private network of the hospital using personal credentials to login. The main functionalities of this application involve:

- visualization of patients' data. These include: symptom monitoring, response to questionnaires, clinical history, monitoring of the performed non pharmacological interventions. Visualization is provided through timelines, views and other suitable graphical representations.
- interaction with guidelines in terms of visualizing recommendations and accepting/declining them.
- prescription of pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions.

Training and information needed to use the technology.

The functional features of the device are described in the user manuals for patients and health professionals. Additionally, the research team organized training sessions involving the health professionals participating in the clinical study and the enrolled patients received in the hospital specific training from the research staff during the enrollment procedures. The technical issues encountered by patients can represent a barrier in the adoption of these interventions, as they can be seen as a possible source of burden for the patients, not directly related with their health status. In the CAPABLE project, we designed a technical support pipeline to minimize the impact on the patients. Problems have anyway arisen, going from specific patients' difficulties linked to technical skills, to generalized problems related to the functioning of the system and of the smartwatch. The implementation of such support pipeline in the two centers might have had an impact on how patients experience such technical issues. In Italy, in fact, a team of biomedical engineers was appointed for the management of technical aspects of the studies, whereas in NKI technical staff of the hospital was only deputed to the management of the deployed IT environment but was not involved in the resolution of technical problems experienced by patients.

Safety aspects

Table 1: Main anticipatable incidental risks

Incidental Risks	Description of the real occurrences during the pilot	How it was managed
Malfunction of the system that delivers wrong/missing recommendation to the patient	Missing recommendations in the Inbox section of the patient mobile app due to synchronization issues between GUI and DP.	Regular contacts between patients and technical contact points in the hospitals allowed i) timely identification of the problem, ii) information of all the patients about the malfunctioning, iii) fixing the issues by developers, iv) communication of the recovery of the system
Malfunction of the system that delivers wrong/missing recommendation to the clinicians	<p>Wrong recommendations were sent on the physician dashboard about the lack of use of the smartwatch by some patients. This was due to synchronization problems on the Asus cloud that did not allow sensor data to be sent to the DP.</p> <p>Missing recommendations on the diarrhea guideline due to an unexpected shutdown of the VM of one component.</p>	<p>Sensor weekly reports allowed timely detecting the real use of the smartwatch by each patient. The responsible of the Sensor module contacted Asus in order to fix the problem. Physicians were informed about the problem and to ignore those wrong recommendations.</p> <p>Thanks to the continuous monitoring log of the components it was possible to detect the issue and reboot the service.</p>
Malfunction of the system that delivers wrong medical indication to the patient	The technical staff has never detected this type of issue, nor it was reported by the patients	Not needed
Patients' misbehaviours such as taking supplements or substances that have not been reported.	No evidence is available to confirm this event happened during the pilot	Patients have always been careful in informing about treatment changes or new prescriptions, even coming from other specialists.
Patient does not report his data	<p>When it comes to self-monitoring, it is difficult to assess whether some information is missing because the patient is not experiencing it or because there is a lack of reporting.</p> <p>In the pilot, the data that were expected at regular time points (questionnaires) have had a very good reporting adherence. For symptoms, we noticed that sometimes, despite the reminders, patients don't report the closure. Also in this case it's difficult to understand if a patient forgot to report or if the symptom is still ongoing.</p>	<p>Patients are trained about the importance of correctly and regularly reporting their data, and this is stressed also in the user manuals of the system. The Virtual coach sends reminders about symptoms monitoring and questionnaires to be filled-in. For periodic questionnaires, the technical staff contacted the patients if the reminders sent by the virtual coach were not sufficient.</p> <p>Technical staff closed some symptoms upon request by some patients who had difficulties</p>

		performing this action through the app.
Patient unintentionally reports the wrong information	Some patients unintentionally inserted a wrong symptom	The oncologists, while checking the dashboard, identified that the reported symptom was not expected for the clinical situation of the patients. The patient was contacted by phone to ask for clarifications and explained the situation. The symptom was immediately closed by the oncologist to avoid the generation of wrong recommendations.
Usability problems prevent or compromise the use of some functionalities of the patient app	The reminders for questionnaires were sent every day if the patient had not filled in the questionnaire. When a reminder is accepted, the others stay anyway in the inbox, thus causing multiple responses.	Patients were trained to fill-in only one questionnaire for each type.
Usability problems prevent or compromise the use of some functionalities on the physician dashboard	A high number of duplicated recommendations was sent to the physician dashboard, due to a wrong configuration of the PDSS. Even though the recommendations that are sent are correct, this might cause the doctor to lose focus on new recommendations.	The PDSS configuration was updated to increase the time between two recommendations of the same type.

Thanks to the monitoring strategies described in deliverable D7.7, we have been able to promptly identify issues related to the malfunctioning of single components, and to some system functionalities. During the clinical study period, the system experienced less problems than in the initial pre-pilot phase (as reported in D7.7). This was achieved thanks to the intensive activity carried out by testers and developers in the deployment sites before the start of the pilot study.

Clinical effectiveness

To assess the effectiveness of the intervention, the study protocols define the quality of life as the main outcome measure. We analyzed differences between the CAPABLE and control cohorts to assess the impact on quality of life when introducing a digital health application with respect to standard care.

Encouraging results were observed in the Italian RCC cohort, showing significantly different trends in overall quality of life, cognitive functioning, fatigue, and appetite loss subscales, as measured by the EORTC QLQ-C30 questionnaire in the CAPABLE and control cohorts. In NKI, no significant adjusted differences on fatigue and other HRQoL domains between the CAPABLE cohort and matched controls during the first 6 months of treatment were identified. However, although not statistically significant, we find that the CAPABLE cohort reported a smaller but clinically relevant increase in fatigue at month 3 follow-up compared to matched controls.

This difference can be partially motivated by considering that we had two different cancer populations, characterized by differences at the baseline as regards overall quality of life (average summary score of 80.8 in RCC vs 90.6 in Melanoma CAPABLE cohorts) and fatigue scores (average FA score of 33.7 in RCC vs 18.4 in Melanoma CAPABLE cohorts).

In contrast to the situation in Italy, the study at NKI revealed notable differences in baseline characteristics across nearly all dimensions of HRQoL between the CAPABLE cohort and their matched controls, suggesting the presence of selection bias.

As regards information satisfaction, we had similar results in Italy and NKI. In NKI, information satisfaction was significantly higher in the CAPABLE users. In Italy, the OVERHELP (Overall the Info has been Helpful) subscale of the INFO25 questionnaire has a significantly different temporal evolution in the two cohorts, with an increasing trend in the CAPABLE group. The CAPABLE app provides some educational content that might have had a positive impact on the perception of the patients in terms of overall information received. Moreover, during the pilot study, patients were supported by a multidisciplinary team that was responsible to give information on different aspects of the system and of the disease. The presence of this multidisciplinary team and their cooperation in the management of the disease had an impact on the quantity and quality of the received information. In the Italian centers, the different specialists (oncologists, psychologists, nutritionists, biomedical engineers) are always available, but during standard care the cooperation among them is only limited to the management of complex situations and there is not a workflow including the systematic referral of patients from the oncology service to the supportive ones.

We found differences in the number and type of symptoms reported in the two studies. While the type of symptoms is related to the treatment that patients undergo (that is different for RCC and Melanoma), the difference in the number and frequency of symptoms suggests that the Melanoma cohort was in a better clinical condition with respect to the RCC cohort.

On the patient side, the overall usability scale has been positively scored by the Italian cohort at T1 and T2 (70.55 and 72.17 over 100) and significantly less by the Dutch cohort (56.15 over 100 at T2). The differences between the results could be explained considering different aspects of the implementation of the CAPABLE services in the Italian and Dutch hospitals and from possible (but not verified) different expectations of the Dutch cohort.

The health professionals from Italy and Netherlands perceived that the CAPABLE solution could add value to the clinical practice (e.g. providing remote monitoring), and the overall level of satisfaction is positive. The study registered lower (but still positive) level of satisfaction in the Dutch health professionals, mostly due to the recurrent technical errors in dashboard (repetition on recommendation and problem in extracting the medication list from the EHR that caused the generation of a long list causing a problem of layout of the dashboard page). The overall system usability has been rated as high with a score of 71.82. A gap on the usability scoring has been identified between Italian and Dutch medical users: in the NKI center the mean score was 65, meanwhile in the Italian centers the average was 75.71.

Costs and economics

The cost analysis of the CAPABLE system has been assessed for the Italian study in which 2 clinical centers from (ICSM Pavia and Policlinico di Bari) tested the solution with 56 patients. (22 in Bari and 34 in Pavia). The costs have been analyzed considering 5 categories, described in the following.

Technology infrastructure

The CAPABLE service has been deployed in a cloud infrastructure managed by ICSM Pavia and accessible also from Policlinico di Bari. The cost of the deployment includes the hosting of 8 virtual machines for an average cost of 870€/ month.

Equipment

The equipment for the patient includes 2 devices: an Android Smartphone (Motorola Edge 20 Lite) and a smartwatch (Asus Vivowatch 5 HC-B05) which has a cost of 275€ and 290€ for patients. Additionally, a SIM card has been provided to grant the internet access from the mobile phone for 6 months (60€).

Other equipment costs (not included in our analysis but relevant to be reported) are the laptops and personal computers needed by the medical team and technical staff to operate with the CAPABLE dashboards and use other applications to support the study (emails, mobile device manager, document processing editors, spreadsheets, EHRs etc.).

Training

The training was performed by the research staff of the CAPABLE project of the UNIPV and ICSM teams. The related cost estimation considers that training day has been of 1 day for each member of the medical team and of 3 days for the technical team.

Clinical efforts

The healthcare professionals needed to carry out the CAPABLE intervention include three different profiles:

1. Oncologists, who are responsible to use the dashboard to remotely follow up the patients. The follow-up of the patients sometimes requires further investigations, carried out through phone calls or email messages sent by the oncologists to the patients (the CAPABLE system does not include a messaging functionality). This work can be estimated to be 1.5 hours a day, considering 60 minutes of usage of CAPABLE and 30 minutes of interactions with patients or IT staff. The oncologist is also involved in the enrollment, and this procedure lasts an average of 1.5 hours for each patient. A total of 4 oncologists were involved in the CAPABLE study in Italy.
2. Dietitian, who is responsible to provide nutritional counseling to the patients, by assessing the patients' nutritional status and following up the patients using CAPABLE according to the changes in their nutritional needs due to treatment and adverse events. The effort for the dietitian can be estimated as follow:
 - a) 90 minutes per week to remotely follow up the patients.
 - b) one 15 minutes call with each patient to provide nutritional counseling support.
 - c) 1 hour for each patient to assess the nutritional needs, divided into 20 minutes for physical assessment, 20 minutes for discuss the physical parameters, and 20 minutes for reporting.
3. Psychologists, who are responsible for providing psychological support for the patients. The effort for the phycologist can be estimated as follow:
 - a) 180 minutes a week to remotely follow up all the patients.
 - b) an average of 3 calls of 15 min for each patient to provide support on the usage of the virtual capsules available in the capable app.
 - c) 1 hour for each patient to assess the psychological status according to the results of the questionnaires available in the app, and to contact patients who required specific assistance.

During the Italian pilot the following clinical team used the CAPABLE technology:

- One oncologist in Pavia acted as proxy for the oncologist taking care of the patient, three oncologists in Bari, the ones that managed directly the patients.
- One dietitian covered the service of the 2 clinical centers.
- Two psychologists, providing support, counseling and referring to the specific clinical psychology unit of the hospital.

Maintenance and support

The technical team was responsible to provide technical support to patients and health professionals and to manage the patient's devices. The activities that supported the CAPABLE study were:

- Technical support at the enrollment: device preparation (1 hour per device), support to the clinician during the enrollment procedure, introduction to the CAPABLE system 2 hours per patient.
- Technical support to patients by phone or during the follow-up visits for technical procedure (app update, device replacements) or to answer questions related to the usage of CAPABLE. 60 min/month per patient for 6 months.

Cost estimation

Technology costs include the costs for servers deployment and the patients' devices as shown in Table 3.

Table 2: Costs of the technology

Description	Unitary cost (€)	Total (€)
Server deployment	870	7,830.00
Mobile Phones	275	15,400.00
Sim cards	60	3,360.00
Wearable sensors	290	16,240.00

The remaining part of the costs depends on the allocated human resources in the previously described groups: oncologists, dietitians, psychologists, and IT managers for that a gross monthly salary has been estimated respectively as 8000€, 7000€, 6000€ and 5000€. According to these costs the following table depicts the costs of the human resources allocated in the hospital for the use of CAPABLE.

Table 3: Costs of the human resources

Role	Procedures	Time (min)	Total time (min)	Cost (€)
Clinician	enrollment time / patient	90	5040	3,952.94
Clinician	follow-up / day	60	16200	12,705.88
Clinician	phone calls to patient or IT staff	30	8100	6,352.94
Psychologist	follow-up / week	180	7020	4,817.65
Psychologist	phone calls to patient	45	2520	1,729.41
Psychologist	clinical assessment	60	3360	2,305.88
Dietitian	follow-up / week	90	3510	2,064.71
Dietitian	phone calls to patient	15	840	494.12
Dietitian	assessment of nutritional needs	60	3360	1,976.47
IT staff	enrollment support	120	6720	3,294.12
IT staff	support to patient	60	20160	9,882.35

	and health professionals / month			
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This estimation has been calculated assuming that the study enrolled 56 patients and the study duration was of 9 months (6 months of active follow-up for each patient and three months for infrastructure set up, training and recruiting activities). The costs of the human resources need to also consider indirect costs that in this estimation are taken as 25%. According to these results the final total cost of the CAPABLE intervention in the Italian study has been 104801€, that represents a cost of 1871€ for each patient.

This estimation includes the real costs of the CAPABLE technology that in the next future could be reduced because of two key technical activities:

- Make the patient app available in the Apple and Google store, to give the opportunity to the patients to install in their own mobile devices. This will allow lowering the costs related to purchasing the smartphones and the costs for the traffic data.
- Simplify the server deployment and reduce the hosting costs.

In a new hypothetical scenario of reducing costs of the hosting to 150€/month, giving the possibility to the patient to install the app in their personal device and purchasing a wearable sensor of 200€ the costs would drop to 1331€/patient.

Ethical analysis

The CAPABLE system is a *medical device* software that *includes AI-based components*, and that is *intended to be used on humans* who are in an impaired clinical situation (oncology patients). These features of the system need to be all considered when performing an assessment of the ethical aspects involved, and of the risks related to such aspects, with the goal of implementing a system that is reliable, safe, technically clear and complete, and managed by well-trained clinical and technical staff.

We summarized possible issues in the following five points, which were addressed during the design and implementation of the system and of the clinical study: (i) informed consent, (ii) potential bias, (iii) incidental findings (iv) use of AI and explainability.

Informed Consent

Informed consent modules have been approved by the Ethical Committee of the clinical sites involved. Their content and the process that must be followed by clinicians respond to ethical international standards such as the protection of autonomy and self-determination, as well as principles of non-nocere, non-maleficence and beneficence.

The consent materials include information about the following elements:

- Secondary findings that are actively sought and returned to participants are conveyed in the informed consent process, with a specific plan for their return.
- A plan for managing incidental findings.
- Possible risks connected to the use of the system and their management, including the contact details of the support in case of malfunctioning or unexpected behavior.

Moreover, obtaining consent from patients is necessary to protect their privacy and their dignity. According to these ethical principles (and not less important, according to European and National laws in the field), the project performed a Data Protection Impact Assessment to analyze risks and to put in place necessary personal data protection measures. Then explicit consent has been asked to patients in order to participate in clinical trials. The content of the consent underwent the evaluation of the DPO of the clinical sites,

the approval of the Ethical Committee and of the National Authorities entitled to consent to the clinical evaluation.

Avoidance of potential biases

The CAPABLE system is a prototype for monitoring cancer patients at home, utilizing AI strategies based on clinical guidelines and predictive models. Concerns about bias led to excluding predictive models from the pilot due to inadequate evaluation of bias sources, generalizability, and model updating. Bias sources include the digital divide, patient selection, and small sample size. The system collects Patients Reported Outcomes (PROMs), subject to various biases like non-response, collection method, and recall. Mitigation strategies involve education, app design, and follow-up. Language and timing biases are addressed through localization and study design. A detailed assessment of the aspects related to bias is presented in deliverable D7.10.

Incidental findings

Incidental findings (IFs) are traditionally defined as results that are outside the original purpose for which a test or procedure was conducted.

The ethical path in the CAPABLE project includes:

- Thinking about anticipatable incidental findings: in Table 1 we present a list of the main anticipatable incidental findings and the number of occurrences in each hospital.
- The informed consent explicitly gives the patients the opportunity either to opt out of receiving information about incidental findings or to withdraw from the study.
- In Italy, the responsibility for the clinical follow-up of the research participant is given to the oncologists involved in the pilot study.

Table 4: Main anticipatable incidental finding

Incidental findings	How it was managed	Subject involved	Occurrences	
			Italy	NKI
From collected data, physicians discover a new disease	The informed consent includes a section on the possibility of anticipatable or unanticipatable cases and how they will be managed. The physician who is taking care of the patient is responsible to inform him/her about the disease.	Physicians	0	0
From collected data, the decision support system reveals a risk of diseases linked to the cancer (e.g. cardiovascular risk)	The informed consent includes a section on the possibility of anticipatable or unanticipatable cases and how they will be managed. The physician who is taking care of the patient is responsible to inform him/her about the disease.	Physicians	0	0

The use of Artificial Intelligence

The CAPABLE system aligns with the European Commission's "Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI" by incorporating five high-level ethical principles: beneficence, non-maleficence, autonomy, justice, and explicability. Here's a summary of how these principles are integrated into the system (the details can be found in deliverable D7.10):

- **Beneficence:** The CAPABLE project, developed with H2020 funding, is designed to benefit users and advance beyond the state of the art. Participatory design involving stakeholders ensures user needs are addressed, and deployment on cloud servers aligns with sustainability policies.
- **Non-maleficence:** Measures are taken to minimize risks related to system malfunction and data processing issues. Validation by healthcare professionals and simulated scenarios ensures system accuracy. Periodic assessment of patient well-being through questionnaires and psychologist supervision is implemented.
- **Autonomy:** Healthcare professionals oversee all system actions, with decisions validated by clinical experts. Treatment recommendations are reviewed and approved by clinicians before implementation.
- **Justice:** Measures are taken to avoid unfair discrimination, promote diversity, and ensure equal access to benefits. Inclusivity in the study is promoted, eligibility criteria are carefully specified, and necessary technology is provided free of charge. Strategies to increase engagement are implemented to address digital health literacy issues.
- **Explicability:** The system's AI applications are developed based on explicit formalization of knowledge from clinical practice guidelines. An explainability component allows for understanding of decision-making processes. Training materials and instructions ensure system functionality is explained for developers, clinicians, and patients.

The predictive models that were developed during the project, even though not included in the system being piloted on real users, are also documented in the deliverables of WP5 (D5.1, D5.2, and D5.4). These documents include the details on the methodology used for training the algorithms (including a description of the input data that was selected), and the information about the validation process.

Organizational aspects

The CAPABLE solution impacts on the management of the cancer patient during the outpatient treatment process. The telehealth feature of the system requires that in the hospital a nurse or oncologist periodically revise the health status of the patient using the CAPABLE dashboard. This is recommended to be done at least once a day.

To deploy the solution in the clinical practice it is necessary to allocate the following resources:

- Research and medical professionals to set up all the authorization to use the technology in the hospital.
- Nurses or health professionals that periodically use the CAPABLE dashboards.

- IT specialists to provide technical support to health professionals and patients. This resource could be internal or external from the hospital and need specific training from the technical team of CAPABLE.

Once the resources have been identified it is crucial to:

- Ensure a proper process of training of the personnel that will use the system.
- Provide the instructions for use to health professionals and patients.
- Allocate resources to buy the wearable sensors (smartwatch) and smartphones in case the enrolled patients cannot install in their own device or do not have any (Note: in the clinical study the hospital also provided a smartphone to the patients, but in future the app will be available to be downloaded in the app stores of Android and IOS).

The last step for the implementation of the solution in a hospital is the deployment of the solution in the hospital infrastructure. This would require the configuration of 2 servers (as Virtual machines) in the hospital infrastructure (the process of deployment has been simplified after the clinical study).

During the clinical study we investigated the barriers for the implementation.

The 2 cohorts of participants (Dutch and Italian) identified the following barriers: the motivation to use CAPABLE, referring to the fact that a successful implementation would require high motivation and involvement of the health professionals (63.6% of responses) as they are responsible for the remote monitoring of the patients. One aspect that could also facilitate the usage is also to understand when it is required to enter in the system, by receiving external reminders (e.g. via mail). Other technical aspects that affected the motivation were the slow loading time of some functionalities of the dashboard (reported as technical errors and currently solved) and the problem of having a long medication list (because of a suboptimal integration with the NKI EHR) in the Dutch dashboards causing the misconfiguration of the dashboard layout. Another identified barrier has been the need for resources (in the 45.5% of the cases from 11 health professionals involved in the CAPABLE study), both human and physical. It is important to allocate specific medical personnel to use the dashboard, specific technical team to provide support to patients and health professionals and have resources to manage the problem with the patient's devices.

One of the main lessons learned during these studies was that the organizational aspects are essential to promote the success of these interventions, which heavily rely on patients' engagement, self-awareness, and motivation. Multidisciplinary teams working in synergy are key enablers to explain the value of the intervention and support the patients through its use. Digital interventions must be coupled with humans to allow positive feedback able to motivate the users to engage with the system and exploit its functionalities, thus adding value to patient care.

Patient and Social aspects

The burden of cancer patients encompasses a wide range of physical, emotional, social, and financial challenges along the whole patient's cancer journey. Below the most relevant issues:

- **Physical Effects:** Cancer and its treatments such as chemotherapy, radiation therapy, and surgery often cause physical discomfort, pain, fatigue, nausea, and other side effects. These can significantly impact a patient's quality of life and ability to perform daily activities.
- **Emotional Impact:** The emotional toll of cancer can be immense, leading to feelings of fear, anxiety, depression, anger, sadness, and uncertainty. Coping with the diagnosis, undergoing treatments, and facing the possibility of recurrence can take a significant emotional toll on patients and their loved ones.
- **Social Challenges:** Cancer can disrupt social relationships and interactions. Patients may experience isolation, stigma, and changes in their roles within their families

and communities. Maintaining social connections and support networks becomes crucial but can also be challenging due to physical limitations and emotional distress.

- **Financial Strain:** The cost of cancer treatment can be substantial, including expenses for medical care, medications, transportation, and other related costs. Additionally, many cancer patients may experience a loss of income due to their inability to work during treatment or caregiving responsibilities. Financial strain can add another layer of stress to an already difficult situation.
- **Impact on Caregivers:** Cancer not only affects patients but also places a significant burden on their caregivers, whether they are family members, friends, or healthcare professionals. Caregivers often face emotional distress, physical exhaustion, financial strain, and disruptions to their own lives as they provide support and assistance to their loved ones.

Overall, the burden of cancer is multifaceted and complex, impacting every aspect of a patient's life and requiring comprehensive support from healthcare providers, caregivers, and the broader community.

The CAPABLE solution is positively perceived by the patients. This has been confirmed both during the design process, when the researchers periodically assessed the perceived value of the solution, and in the final clinical study (see D.7.2, D7.3, D7.4 and D7.8). The overall perception of the solution has been assessed in the final clinical study using the uMARS instruments and the overall score was positive in both cohorts: the Italian cohort registered a mean of 4.1 (min 2.9, max 4.8 st.dev 0.53) and the Dutch one a mean of 3 (min 1 max 3.9 st.dev 0.86), in a range between 1 and 5. The instruments consider dimensions as engagements, functionality, aesthetics, information.

Caregivers

The CAPABLE system supports the option that a caregiver could report a symptom of the patients. This sometimes is needed because the patient is not able to respond himself due to physical or cognitive problems. In Italy, 29 out of 56 patients declared to have a caregiver because of their health status, in NKI none of the patients reported having a caregiver. To consider this possible situation, the reporting symptoms functionality in the CAPABLE app allows users to check a flag if the symptom is reported by caregivers. We do not have evidence of questionnaires filled in by others other than the patients themselves, so we couldn't assess the impact of this possible bias in our study. In case we had questionnaires or symptoms reported by caregivers, we would have considered the data separately and evaluate if any difference was detectable in the responses.

During the CAPABLE study, we used the Caregiver Burden Inventory (CBI) questionnaire to assess the caregiver burden profiles in the Italian study cohort. CBI is a multidimensional measurement that measures caregiver burden with 5 subscales considering physical, psychological, emotional, social and financial problems. CBI consists of 24 questions, and each item is evaluated using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 0 (not at all disruptive) to 4 (very disruptive). A total score >36 indicates a risk of burning out, whereas scores >=24 indicate a need to seek for support. Out of the 29 collected answers, we found that 26 caregivers (89.6%) reported a low burden level (<24), 1 reported a moderate level, and 2 a high burden. Considering that, overall, the 51.8% of the patients had a caregiver, and that out of these the 89.6% reported a low caregiver burden, the CAPABLE Italian cohort was not highly dependent on the caregivers, making difficult to assess the impact of the CAPABLE intervention in the management of patients by their caregivers.

Legal aspects

Since the CAPABLE system is a software that deals with the processing of health-related data, it has to comply with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Medical Device Regulation (MDR). In addition, since the pilot study involves human subjects, an approval by the Ethical Committees is mandatory.

According to Article 35 of the GDPR, a Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIA) is required as part of the protection by design principle, since the type of processing performed by the CAPABLE system involves new technologies and personal data: "racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation". One of the requirements of the DPIA is the definition of the roles and responsibilities of all the parties involved in the data processing. For the CAPABLE study, together with the Data Protection Officers (DPOs) of the hospitals, we identified the following roles: the hospitals responsible for running the clinical study act as Data Controller, whereas the project partners are appointed as Data Processors.

According to Article 62 of the Medical Device Regulation (MDR), CAPABLE clinical investigation has the purpose to "establish and verify the clinical benefits of a device as specified by its manufacturer". Since the CAPABLE system is classified as a class IIa medical device without CE marking, the clinical investigation must undergo an authorization process in each country where it is carried out. This procedure is specified in the MDR and required similar documentation both in Italy and in the Netherlands.

To comply with the requirements described above the following steps have been necessary during the project:

1.Preparation of the DPIA

For each data processing site, one DPIA document was prepared and signed by the Data Controller. The document includes a technical description of the CAPABLE system and of the data flow, the description of all the data processing involved, the roles and responsibilities of the parties involved, and a description and assessment of risks and measures to mitigate them. According to the decision to appoint partners as Data Processors, Data Transfer Agreements (DTA) were prepared and signed by the legal representatives of each institution. To be eligible as a Data Processor, each partner had to fill in and sign a Security Checklist about the security measures available at its institution.

2.Preparation of the Ethical Committee documentation

After finalizing the DPIA, the next step was the preparation of the documentation needed for Ethical Committee approval. The main documents requested by the Ethical Committees of the hospitals were: the clinical protocol, the informed consent, the privacy statement, and the DPIA.

3.Preparation of the submission for the Medical Device Registration

To be able to submit the documentation for authorization of the clinical investigation according to MDR, the Italian procedure requests a preliminary approval by the Ethical Committee. The documentation is then submitted to the Italian Ministry of Health. In the Netherlands, the documentation must be submitted to the Central Committee on Research Involving Human Subjects (CCMO). CCMO approval is needed to proceed to the Ethical Committee submission. Documentation was prepared and approved by the National Authorities before starting the clinical studies.

If CAPABLE will become a certified MDR product the required steps to adopt the solution in a hospital would be necessary to complete the first two steps. The legal entity responsible for the CAPABLE service would have the required experience and skills to complete the procedure.

Standardization aspects

Standardization aspects were the focus of Task 8.3. There were two activities related to standardization:

- Standardise novel project outputs or use them to extend existing standards and make sure CAPABLE remains aligned with current European and international standards.
- Focus on obtaining certification of the European Medical Device Regulation (MDR)
 - Understand and meet the requirements for the pilot studies under the MDR.
 - Understand the requirements for bringing CAPABLE to market and prepare for this next step.

Strategy of standardization in CAPABLE

Use of existing standards: CAPABLE makes extensive use of existing EU, international, and domain-specific standards.

OMOP: The Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model is an open community data standard, developed as a result of the OHDSI project. It is designed to standardize the structure and content of medical data, so it can be reliably used by various software components. CAPABLE uses OMOP for storing data in the Data Platform.

HL7 FHIR: The Health Level 7 Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources standard is designed to be a practical standard for exchanging health care data. Its focus was on ease of implementation for health software, with strong foundations in widely adopted web standards such as XML and JSON. CAPABLE uses FHIR for all its communication between components.

OMOP-FHIR mapping: The open source OMOP-on-FHIR¹⁸ project aims to create a mapping between OMOP and FHIR. CAPABLE uses this work as a starting point and has extended the mapping to include the clinical data needed by CAPABLE.

SNOMED CT: SNOMED-CT is a merger of the Systematized Nomenclature Of Medicine and Clinical Terms Version 3, and it is a systematically organized computer-interpretable collection of medical terms providing codes, terms, synonyms and definitions. It is the most complete medical terminology system and includes codes for most relevant medical concepts. CAPABLE uses SNOMED-CT for specification of all the clinical concepts in (for example) the Computer Interpretable Guidelines.

RxNorm: "Medical prescription, normalized" is a terminology system that contains codes for all the medications available on the US market. It includes codes at the product and ingredient level, making it useful for applications such as drug interaction checking. CAPABLE uses RxNorm for representing logic about medications, such as medication interaction checking.

ATC codes: The Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical codes are an international coding system for medications, at the level of generic ingredient. It is the most-widely-used standard for medication coding in Europe. Because medications are stored with ATC codes in most European electronic health records, CAPABLE can extract and interpret medications coded using this system.

¹⁸ <https://github.com/omoponfhir>

CTCAE: The Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events is a system of grading the severity of adverse events from (for example) immunotherapy or other chemotherapy. The PRO-CTCAE is a derivative system for patient self-reporting of adverse event symptoms. CAPABLE uses the CTCAE for clinician grading of adverse events for use by the decision support logic, and uses a curated subset of 122 CTCAE symptoms for patient reporting.

CAPABLE partners are also aligned with standards relevant to the Medical Device Regulation and the GDPR.

Contributions to standards: CAPABLE has also made several contributions to the standards listed above, as well as others:

PRO-CTCAE: The PRO-CTCAE did not include all of the adverse events that could be experienced by patients undergoing immunotherapy or chemotherapy. We extended the PRO-CTCAE to include all of the patient-reportable symptoms of the CTCAE, using patient-friendly terms. Importantly, we made sure that the descriptions were sufficiently distinct that a patient could easily tell which category to pick. These used to provide a symptom level for the decision support system to use in its logic. Another innovation of CAPABLE was to create a patient-friendly digital interface for patient self-reporting of symptoms. This will be disseminated in a publication, currently in preparation by UNIPV, ICSM, NKI, AMC.

SNOMED-CT: Although SNOMED-CT has more than 350,000 terms, we still identified a few concepts that were missing from SNOMED-CT. We submitted a request to extend SNOMED-CT to include "IV rehydration therapy".

OMOP-FHIR mapping: We have extended the OMOP-FHIR mapping with additional concepts, and plan to contribute these additions upstream.

SATO ontology: SATO stands for ideaS expANded wiTh bicO, and is based on the IDEAS (Integrate, Design, Assess, and Share) framework aligned with the Behaviour Change Intervention Ontology. It is an ontology specifically for designers of patient-centered mobile health behaviour change intervention applications. CAPABLE extended this ontology with concepts required to implement the behavior change interventions in CAPABLE¹⁹:

OWL ontology for point rewards: The point reward system used by CAPABLE is being formalized into an ontology, which will be contributed to SATO and to the Gamification Domain Ontology (GaDO).

RxNorm-ATC mapping: Because CAPABLE uses the more specific RxNorm codes in its internal logic, we created a mapping between RxNorm and ATC codes. This will be disseminated in a scientific publication.

BioMedSci AI: This project aims to accelerate scientific discovery in biomedical sciences through developing tools that help researchers²⁰. IBM has been contributing to this open-source project, particularly in AI tools for drug discovery, chemical substructures, multi-modal models, and genomics data analysis.

Guideline metadata and metaproperties: Computer-interpretable guidelines play a central role in CAPABLE (as well as other decision support applications), but there is currently no way to describe the contents of a computer-interpretable guideline so as to make it FAIR. We are working on establishing a standard description of a computer

¹⁹ <https://w3id.org/CAPABLE/ontologies/SATO>

²⁰ <https://github.com/BiomedSciAI/>

interpretable guideline, and describing our own CIGs using this model. As a part of this project, we are developing a small **ontology of guideline languages**.

Roadmap to certification of the European Medical Device Regulation (MDR)

This sub-task consisted of two steps:

1. Meet the requirements for the pilot studies under the MDR
2. Requirements for bringing CAPABLE to market and prepare for this next step

1. Meet the requirements for the pilot studies under the MDR

This project started just as the new MDR came into effect. The first step was to ensure that the consortium was aware of the implications of the new MDR for this project. When it became clear that the MDR would affect not only the exploitation of CAPABLE but also its development and the clinical pilot study, we formed Task Force 4, a working group that included members from all organizations and work packages that would be involved in ensuring compliance with the MDR.

With the help of the Medical Device office at NKI, and the National Authorities in both the Netherlands (the Central Commission for Human Research, CCMO) and Italy (Ministry of Health), we determined the steps that would be needed for CAPABLE before the start of the pilot study. Italy requires all clinical trials to be registered as Article 62 studies; considering that this also puts CAPABLE in a better position for exploitation, we registered both pilot studies under Article 62. As required to register the study as an article 62 clinical investigation, we created the following documents:

- Eudamed form.
- Investigator's brochure.
- Investigational Medical Device Dossier (IMDD).
- Instructions for use (in Dutch and Italian).
- Signed statement by the Manufacturer.
- Clinical Evaluation Plan (pertaining to this study).

Together with a submission form, the study protocol, the Subject information sheets and informed consent forms, questionnaires, proof of insurance, the site suitability declaration, CVs of the principal investigators, and the Data Protection Impact Assessment, these documents were submitted to the National Authority in the Netherlands and Italy, and to the ethics committees of the respective study centers. These requirements were met in time for the studies to be approved before the scheduled study start date. Details of this process are described in D7.6 and the documentation is available as an annex to that deliverable.

2. Requirements for bringing CAPABLE to market and prepare for this next step

Before a system like CAPABLE can be exploited as a commercial product, a CE mark must be obtained. The path to doing so is unclear, particularly for researchers (since their organization may not be able to hold a CE mark for software) but also for SMEs who do not yet have experience with this process.

To help alleviate some of this uncertainty, we produced a guidance document for use by consortium members. Since other research projects are likely experiencing the same barriers to exploitation, we also plan to publish a version of this document (including a section on "lessons learned" from CAPABLE's experience with the MDR so far). The guidance document contains the following information:

1. Lessons learned, including:

- There is a low threshold for classifying software medical devices in a higher risk class.
- The MDR includes requirements for the software development process.
- There is more than one way to register a medical device study, and between-country differences in the process.
- The manufacturer and sponsor have specific requirements and responsibilities.
- Only the medical device functionality needs to be certified.
- The hospital medical device office and national competent authority can help.

2. Roadmap for the next steps, including:

- Determine who is/are the manufacturer(s) and what functionality will be certified.
- Ensure required processes are in place (with certifications if needed)
- Determine the country and obtain funding.
- Assemble the Technical Documentation / Technical File.
- Prepare to do required support, post-market surveillance, and follow-up.

The working copy document is available internally for consortium members.

Conclusions and future work

The document presented a report of the health technology assessment activities, following the methods proposed by the EU HTA network.

The overall assessment of the technology demonstrates it to be a viable candidate to be a digital product and this is in line with the clinical results achieved and with the market trends and the current competitors in the market.

The proposed methodology analyzed the aspects related to the current clinical problem of cancer management and existing solutions, the proposed solution, safety, and ethical aspects that need to be considered and the clinical effectiveness. The clinical study has a reduced clinical impact but shows promising results in terms of improvement of QoL of the patients. On the end user's side, the level of satisfaction has been positive. The Cost and economics sections details the operationalization costs of the CAPABLE solution considering the required human resources and technical equipment, but it was not possible to perform a cost benefit analysis since it was not possible to access the clinical information on visits, referral to other specialists, changes in treatment etc.

On the organizational side it is important to highlight the importance of proper human resources to grant the proper technical support to the end users, this could jeopardize the performance and the acceptance of the solution in the clinical practice, as it has been experienced in the Dutch pilot. Patients and social aspects are also other important dimensions to consider in which the proposed solution would provide a significant contribution to support the burden of the patients and offer to the caregiver the possibility to support the patient through the technology. Finally, the legal aspect detailed the legal framework to be followed to use this solution for research purposes. This very final overview of the CAPABLE experience is an opportunity for the Consortium to start looking at the next steps to increase the level of maturity of the technology as described in D8.7. In the context of this document one significant aspect has been considered, that is the level of standardization of the CAPABLE technology, that has been defined from the beginning as a very highly interoperable solution adopting State of the Art medical standards and terminologies. During the project many standards have been adopted and improved and extended, generating different types of assets that would be useful for the future works of the consortium.